

A NEW ALUMINA FIBRE FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITES.

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ABSTRACT

A potentially cheap, fine diameter, semi-continuous alumina fibre with attractive physical and chemical properties for advanced composites is being developed. The fibre ("Safimax" alumina) is available in two grades - a low density grade (2.0 g/ml) and a high density grade (3.3 g/ml). Both grades have high strength and modulus. The fibres have a polycrystalline microstructure and are produced as a semi-continuous multistrand tow or blanket with a high degree of alignment of fibres (3 μm diameter) with respect to each other, permitting the development of high volume fraction unidirectional or 2-D laminated composites. The process when scaled up is expected to give material at attractively low prices (50-75 \$/lb).

Preliminary results are reported for "Safimax" fibre in resin matrix and in metal matrix composites. The fibres show good compatibility with these matrices and the composites have rule-of-mixtures values for the modulus. Applications are foreseen principally in aerospace, auto, and electrical engineering markets.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre/resin composites are ideally suited for lightweight load-bearing structures which are not exposed to temperatures above 150°C. At higher temperatures metals and ceramics are preferred since thermally-stable, inexpensive, low-density non metallic composites have not yet been developed. MMCs are the most promising class of thermally-stable composites. Carbon fibres are difficult to use in MMCs

since they are generally reactive towards both Al and Mg and cause electrolytic corrosion in aqueous environments. Consequently attempts have been made both to develop inert coatings for carbon fibres and to develop alternative fibres. So far cheap, suitably-coated carbon fibres have not been achieved. But various alternative fibres have been made available.

In order to develop the highest stiffness in an MMC a high volume fraction of fibres is necessary and this calls for a straight and long fibre. Over the last two decades several continuous, multifilament products have been developed having specific mechanical properties similar to those of carbon fibres but with greater chemical stability towards metals. Impressive technical performance has been reported for boron fibres (Avco), for silicon carbide fibres (Nippon carbon, Ube, Avco), and for aluminas (Du Pont) or alumino-silicates (Sumitomo). But since all these products are made on pilot plants, their current prices are relatively high (200-600 \$/lb).

For low temperature duties where there is a need for high electrical insulation, carbon fibres are no longer appropriate. Kevlar fibres or glass fibres in resins are widely used but there is scope for use of stiffer, low dielectric constant fibres to give lightweight composites suitable for electrical and electronic engineering applications (e.g. in radomes)

We describe below a novel high-alumina semi-continuous fibre which is expected to be available initially within the price range of \$50-75/lb. This will open up possibilities for cheaper MMCs with good medium temperature performance (to 300°C) having the load-bearing properties of steel but at around third the weight. These materials should lead to significant energy savings in aerospace and auto applications at more economical costs than hitherto. Because alumina is a good dielectric material, there should also be applications in resin composites for the electrical engineering industry. This paper describes the properties of the fibres themselves and methods of making composites from them. Preliminary data are also given for the properties of MMCs using three alloys and of epoxy resin composites.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The novel fibres are synthesised by a proprietary process which is

the subject of world-wide patent applications. The primary product is a non-woven semi-continuous aligned high alumina fibre blanket (trademark "Safimax" alumina fibre). Multi-filament tows and wovens are under development. The fibre composition is 4% silica/96% alumina. Two grades are available having different fibre densities and crystallinities.

Individual fibre properties have been established by standard physical tests where possible. Mechanical properties were determined using a Marsh Microtensile machine (1 mm gauge length) [1]. Density was determined by helium pycnometry and by flotation in Clerici solutions. Fibre porosity was measured using nitrogen adsorption isotherms. Diameter measurements were by optical microscopy using a micrometer eyepiece.

MMC preparation

For the purpose of making small discrete components (in this case test specimens) liquid infiltration of metal into a fibre preform is the preferred method. The fibre preform is a rigidised shape containing the fibres in the correct packing and orientation for the final component (in this case unidirectional). This enables simple one-part die-casting moulds to be used for making the MMC. We have investigated the use of both fugitive and refractory binders for making unidirectional 30-60 vol % "Safimax" fibre preforms.

Fugitive binder technique

"Safimax" fibre blankets are weighed and cut to length and strips laid up in a simple 2-part cylindrical mould. The mould is closed to compress the fibre to 50 vol % and "Modar" 835 methacrylate resin (RTM) is drawn by vacuum through the preform parallel to the fibres. The resin is cold-cured for 2 hrs (or less by warming) and the preform is then removed from the mould. The preform was then machined to an exact fit into a metal-casting die and heated to 800°C, causing the resin to burn out and allowing the fibre to exert a force on the mould walls. Molten metal is then introduced into the preheated fibre-filled mould in the same direction as the fibre axes. The partially-compressed fibres have sufficient resilience to remain in place while the molten metal is squeezed through the packed fibre at 30 MPa (Fig 1).

Suitable tensile and 3-point bend specimens were then machined from the blanks using diamond tipped tools.

Figure 1. Multicaster Schematic Layout
Refractory Binder Technique

When lower volume fractions (30-40%) of "Safimax" alumina fibres are required where the fibres do not exert much pressure on mould walls, then a refractory binder is necessary. Instead of infiltrating the compressed "Safimax" fibre with resin, a solution of 5% colloidal silica flocculated with starch is used. After drying at above 110°C for 4 hrs, the preform is fired at 1200°C for 2 hrs. The silica bonds the fibres at points where they touch. The fired preform can be machined to size before inserting into the die.

Epoxy resin composite preparation

The resin used was Shell Epikote 828 (100 g) with NMA hardener (90 g) and Epicure K61B accelerator (1.9 g). 15x15x0.3 cm sheets have been made by both wet lay-up technique and by prepreg lay-up. In both cases fibres were unidirectional. Prepreg was made by dipping tows of fibre into a 10 v/v % dichloromethane solution of the mixed resin and then drying in a vacuum oven at 50°C. The lay-ups were made in a suitable two-part metal mould which could then be compressed to the desired thickness in a heated-platten press. In the case of prepreg layup a standard vacuum bag technique was used with a modified mould to allow for a high degree of compression. A pressure of ca 3.5 MPa at 60°C was sufficient to reach fibre volume fractions of about 50%. The sheets were heated under pressure for 2 hrs at 100°C and for 16 hrs at 150°C.

The sheet was cut up using a diamond tipped circular saw into 1 cm wide strips for 3-point bending test or for tensile tests. Edges of the composite strips were polished on a wheel using 600 grit silicon carbide paper.

Mechanical Testing

For tests under ambient conditions, a model 1185 Instron tester was used. For testing MMCs at temperature a heated cell was employed.

RESULTS

Fibre Properties

Average tensile properties from tests on 20 fibres for fibre diameter, strength, and modulus are given in Table 1 for both grades of fibre. In both cases the fibres have a median diameter of nominally 3 μm .

Table 1
"Safimax" Alumina Fibre Properties

Grade	Diameter microns	Modulus GPa	Strength MPa
SD	3.1+-0.9	250+-25	2000+-350
LD	3.2+-0.9	207+-20	2000+-320

Individual fibre diameters lie in the range 2-5 μm . The standard density (SD) grade fibres are delta/theta alumina and have a density of 3.3 g/ml. Low density (LD) grade fibres are eta-alumina with a fibre density of 2.0 g/ml (porosity 35%). Maximum individual fibre lengths are 1.5-2 m but fibre tows are coherent due to the fine diameter. An SEM of an SD fibre bundle is shown in Fig 2 from which it can be seen that the fibre surface is extremely smooth and that the alignment of fibres is good. The alignment of fibres within the blanket is 90% within $\pm 10^\circ$. The blanket is loosely packed with about 10 vol% fibres but modest compressive force increases the packing to 50-60 vol% without significant fibre damage. The packing properties of the blanket are demonstrated in Fig 3 where it can be seen that modest pressures enable high volume fractions of fibre to be achieved. The pressure exerted by "Safimax" fibre bundles at high volume fractions is an advantage in liquid infiltration processes for making composites since there is no necessity to use a binder to hold fibres in place. However for lower

volume fraction composites refractory binders have been used to create rigid preforms.

Figure 2. SD "Safimax" Fibres

Figure 3. Compressibility of SD "Safimax" fibres

The strength of "Safimax" fibres is essentially independent of fibre density. There is a modest increase in fibre stiffness with density. It follows from the fibre densities that the LD fibres have the best specific properties. These are compared in Table 2 with the values of other continuous fibres. The "Safimax" fibres demonstrate an attractive combination of stiffness and density which is more marked if the specific stiffness for bending or buckling geometries are considered (i.e. $E^{1/2}/\rho$ or $E^{1/3}/\rho$).

Table 2
Specific Properties of Inorganic Fibres

Material	Density g/ml	Specific Modulus	Specific Strength
LD "Safimax" Alumina	2.0	100	1000
SD "Safimax" Alumina	3.3	76	600
"FP" fibers (du Pont)	4.0	97	330
Sumitomo alumina	3.2	62	470
"Nextel" 440	3.1	71	550
"Nicalon" SiC	2.6	71	1040
"Tyranno" fibres	2.35	89	1230
AVCO SCS2	3.0	140	1330
AVCO Boron	2.4	162	1600

As a consequence of these properties and their fine diameter the fibres have excellent flexibility. This is expected to allow in the long term complex layups around tight corners and to lead to yarns which will be easy to weave. The creation of custom-designed fibre preforms of complex shape should be possible.

Metal Matrix Composites

MMCs have previously been successfully made using ICI RF-grade "Saffil" random alumina fibres. Chemically these are close relatives to SD grade "Safimax" alumina fibres[2]. The technology established for "Saffil" alumina MMCs is the formation of a short fibre, silica-bound, low volume fraction rigid preform. The MMC is then created by placing the preform into a preheated mould and squeeze-casting the matrix alloy so as to infiltrate the preform efficiently[3].

Because of their different packing properties and their fine diameter, a modified preform method has been found to be suitable for "Safimax" alumina fibres. Because of the pressure exerted on any container by high volume fractions of "Safimax" fibres there is no necessity to employ a refractory binder. All that is required is a technique for filling a mould with the required amount of fibre having the desired orientation. The method described above achieves the effect conveniently using a fugitive methacrylate binder. Once the mould (a simple tube in this work) is filled with fibre then the molten metal can be infiltrated by squeezing to 30 MPa. This technique is suitable for making tensile (dogbone) samples and 3-point bending test samples.

Four matrix alloys have been investigated so far with SD grade "Safimax" fibres i.e. LM10, 2024, 6061, and CP Mg. The results for mechanical testing are given in Tables, 3 and 4.

The variation of composite modulus with fibre volume fraction are compared, Table 3. It is clear that the expected rule-of-mixtures modulus has been obtained in these MMCs. The effective modulus of the SD "Safimax" fibres in the MMCs is 300 GPa and that of the LD grade is 220 GPa. These are in line with the values found from testing the fibres themselves. The tensile strengths of some composites were found to be lower than predicted. Sumitomo fibres were substituted for Safimax fibres and also demonstrated reduced strengths. Defects may have been induced in the composites during manufacture. Clifford[4] has demonstrated that reduced strength may be caused by machining of cast components.

Table 3
Effect of "Safimax" Fibres on Composite Modulus at Ambient Temperatures

Fibre	Vol. Fraction V_f	Matrix	Tensile Modulus GPa	Comp. Modulus GPa
SD	.37	2024	169	169
"	.46	2024	190	182
"	.35	LM10	161	136
"	.48	LM10	199	178
"	.30	CP Mg	123	
"	.48	CP Mg	151	
"	.50	6061	185	
LD	.57	6061	160	
SUMITOMO	.45	6061	154	

Subsequent Safimax fibre "cast to shape" test pieces have demonstrated vastly improved strengths. However it is apparent that composite toughness must be further considered. Typically for $> 0.5V_f$ composites the transverse strength is in line with that expected. Compressive strengths are also good indicating that the fibres resist buckling and shear damage. As expected these properties are also well-maintained up to 300°C.

Examination of tensile fracture faces and axial sections in the test specimens by SEM and optical microscopy shows that the microstructures are reasonably uniform. Fracture faces show evidence of matrix ductility. Failure occurs via a ductile/dimple mode. The fibre

Figure 4. Fracture Surface of SD "Safimax" fibre/2024 Composite

acting as a particulate and initiating failure Fig. 4.[5]

As process development proceeds these difficulties are expected to be eliminated. SEMs of fracture faces and polished sections show that the castings have good integrity and that there is no attack on the fibres. Only in the case of Mg-infiltrated, silica-bound preforms has any evidence of attack been found and then only on the silica binder resulting in undesirable formation of intermetallic Mg_2Si phase which concentrates at the bottom of the casting[6].

Table 4 shows the coefficient of thermal expansion for an SD "Safimax"/alloy composite. As is usually the case the value is low relative to that of the alloy.

Table 4
Coefficients of Thermal Expansion of "Safimax" Alumina
Al Alloy Composites

Composite	Vf of Fibre	Thermal Expansion $10^{-6} K^{-1}$	
		Fibre Alignment	
		In Plane	Normal
RF Saffil in Al-9Si-3Cu 20°C - 200°C	0	20.3	20.3
	0.12	16.3	17.6
	0.24	15.5	15.7
SD "Safimax" fibre in 2024 at 350°C	0.37	10.0	25.5
	0.48	7.4	21.5

Epoxy Composites

Unidirectional composites have been tested at 0° and 90° to the fibre direction. Tensile and 3-point bending results are given in Table 5. The transverse results are dominated by the resin properties and indicate that a satisfactory interfacial bond strength is achieved. The 0° tensile results indicate that at least 70% of the rule-of-mixtures

Table 5
48% by vol SD "Safimax" Alumina/Epoxy Composite
Mechanical Properties

Tensile Tests				Flexural Tests	
0°		90°		0°	
E/GPa	TS/MPa	E/GPa	TS/MPa	E/GPa	FS/MPa
83+-6	206+-10	10.8+-1	154+-1.2	59+-14	265+-45

modulus has been realised. The strengths were 200-300 MPa but presumably here fracture will be dominated by fibre strength and aspect ratio rather than by matrix strength. Microscopic evidence shows that the "Safimax" fibres are easy to wet and have good fibre-resin adhesion but that wet layups are difficult to degas satisfactorily. These findings may indicate that fibre damage during wet layup and moulding is unacceptable leading to low aspect ratio fibres. Vacuum consolidation of prepreg shows promise in overcoming the degassing problem and is more precise in attaining the correct proportions of fibre and resin.

The dielectric constant and loss tangent for a 50 vol % SD "Safimax" fibre/epoxy resin composite was measured over the frequency range 10 KHz to 5 MHz. The results are in Table 6.

The values are as expected for a resin alumina composite.

Table 6
52% by vol SD "Safimax" Alumina fibre/Epoxy Composite
Dielectric Properties

Frequency/kHz	Dielectric Constant	tan delta
10	6.93	0.0130
30	6.86	0.0119
50	6.82	0.0129
100	6.77	0.0135
300	6.72	0.0145
500	6.69	0.0157
1000	6.66	0.0185
3000	6.87	0.0284

DISCUSSION

"Safimax" alumina fibres differ from other products on the market in three main respects; they are relatively cheap, of fine diameter (and hence flexible) and of low density. Like "Saffil" alumina fibres they have excellent resistance to molten light alloys. They are also wetted by and adhere readily to epoxy resin. The specific fibre load-bearing properties are excellent for high volume fraction composites.

In making MMCs and resin composites, rigid preforms and prepreg techniques respectively are advantageous because the "Safimax" fibre blankets are so flexible. For high volume fractions a fugitive binder is useful since it eliminates reaction between an aggressive matrix and binder. For lower volume fractions refractory-bound preforms do not require any external constraining forces and are more flexible in use. They may be used for local reinforcement of large castings.

At present the theoretical stiffness has been realised in light-alloy MMCs up to 300°C utilising squeeze-casting for liquid infiltration. Although the expected tensile strengths have not yet been fully achieved, these composites do have excellent compressive strength. Secondary properties of importance are low coefficient of thermal expansion and reduced thermal conductivity. The stiffness properties compare well with those of titanium and steel and because of the low MMC density there is potential for reducing the weight of such components by greater than 50%. This is likely to be of initial interest for engine support frames in aircraft and for gearbox, compressor, and fuel pump parts.

Fatigue properties have yet to be assessed but are unlikely to be a limitation on such uses. The preferred use of squeeze-casting techniques for fabrication indicates that small discrete components are likely to benefit initially. These may be of relatively complex shape once fibre preforms to suit the moulds have been developed.

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